

D1.7 – Use-Case requirements

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D1.7 Use-Case requirements

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Task leader/Main author	Alberto Palomero (HRS)
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Reviewer(s)	Gabor Sziebig (SINTEF)

Abstract

The objective in this section is to evaluate and list the BIMprove requirements for future implementation in any construction project. For that purpose, the following outputs are expected:

- Definitions of use cases (current, desired and achievable state)
- List of new tasks or tasks modified by BIMprove
- Table of requirements per task listed

To avoid a complete re-evaluation of the construction branch, we will focus on those tasks completely new as well as those modified by BIMprove comparing to a BIM based or traditional construction methodologies.

The reviews will focus on, but not be limited to, specific use cases, i.e., fire, security, and scheduling. This means, while the industrial partners focus their analysis on the pilot use cases, the entire consortium will evaluate the possibility of developing new tasks, as well as the possible modification of the tasks currently developed without the use of BIMprove.

Keywords

BIMprove, tasks, functionalities, BIM requirement, BIMprove requisites, PUC, state of the art, achievable state, desired state, fire, safety, scheduling

Revisions

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
BIM	Building Information Modelling
PUC	Pilot Use Case
Achievable state	realistic, viable within a given time and conditions
Desired state	To be reached. Perfect. It may or may not be utopian or unattainable under current conditions.
CPE	Collective protective equipment
H&S	Health and Safety
ACSS	H&S commission minutes
IDI	Accident investigation report
IMS	Monthly accident rate report
INC	no conformity report
ICTO	Site working conditions in site report
XR	Extended Realities. Refers to Virtual, Augmented and Mixed reality
MR	Mixed Reality
AR	Augmented Reality
VR	Virtual Reality

BIMprove project

In the past 20 years, productivity in the European construction industry has increased by 1% annually only, which is at the lower end compared to other industrial sectors. Consequently, the sector has to step up its digitization efforts significantly, on the one hand to increase its competitiveness and on the other hand to get rid of its image as dirty, dangerous and physical demanding working environment. Construction industry clearly needs to progress beyond Building Information Modelling when it comes to digitizing their processes in such a way that all stakeholders involved in the construction process can be involved.

The true potential of comprehensive digitization in construction can only be exploited if the current status of the construction work is digitally integrated in a common workflow. A Digital Twin provides construction companies with real-time data on the development of their assets, devices and products during creation and also enables predictions on workforce, material and costs.

BIMprove facilitates such a comprehensive end-to-end digital thread using autonomous tracking systems to continuously identify deviations and update the Digital Twin accordingly. In addition, locations of construction site personnel are tracked anonymously, so that **BIMprove** system services are able to optimize the allocation of resources, the flow of people and the safety of the employees. Information will be easily accessible for all user groups by providing personalized interfaces, such as wearable devices for alerts or VR visualizations for site managers. **BIMprove** is a cloud-based service-oriented system that has a multi-layered structure and enables extensions to be added at any time.

The main goals of **BIMprove** are a significant reduction in costs, better use of resources and fewer accidents on construction sites. By providing a complete digital workflow, BIMprove will help to sustainably improve the productivity and image of the European construction industry.

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1. Introduction

The analysis of the requirements is a fundamental part of any technological or methodological development since it will guarantee users the correct execution and implementation in specific projects of any kind.

Due to the impossibility of analysing the entire construction branch, it is intended to perform a delta analysis, that is, only analysing what BIMprove changes or incorporates into the current system, understanding as a current system, constructions under the BIM methodology.

In order to perform the delta analysis, it will be necessary to specify a list of specific tasks or functionalities that can be executed after the implementation of BIMprove in the pilot projects. These tasks must be grouped within a realistic and pragmatic framework, which ensures an achievable improvement compared to the current state of each of the use cases to be evaluated. To do this, we start from a concrete definition of the current and desired states, with an emphasis on the achievable state of the use cases. That is, the intermediate, realistic and pragmatic point of improvement between the current and desired states, which is viable and can be implemented within the duration of the research project.

2. Current state of the art

A first definition of the current state of each PUC. What is the purpose of the use case? What processes and tasks are developed? How many specialists carry them out? What roles do they play? What software / hardware or other tools are necessary for the execution of these tasks? And finally, where are the problems or limitations of the process?

Knowing the starting point is essential to know the direction in which to advance.

2.1. Pilot Use Case Fire

The goal is to make prevention and intervention plans and ensure their compliance to avoid risky situations. If a risk situation arises, execute the protocol as quickly as possible, including, if necessary, communication with authorities and client.

There are 3 key pillars in fire prevention and it is important to note that they all play a fundamental role preventing hazard situations:

- **Fire & safety manager:** is the final person in charge in case of accident or fire. He is in charge of analysing the future construction and presenting to the authorities a fire protection plan adapted to the needs of the work. This plan will be implemented and updated if necessary. Periodically, this person in charge must visit the work to carry out exhaustive controls, as well

as technical reviews of different aspects (Storage of combustible materials, general state of the work, entrances and exits or dangerous operations, among others).

- Construction manager: This role will implement the fire and safety plan in a day-to-day work, approving and supervising dangerous tasks, monitoring emergency exits and ensure that people comply with local regulations among others.
- The different workers within the construction area: The key to success resides here. It is essential that they know the regulations and are properly trained. They must know which are the dangerous areas, what security measures they must take, where the deposits of flammable substances are located, etc ...

If any of the three pillars fails, the potentially dangerous situations increase exponentially

The tasks begin with the creation of the protection plan. This plan, adapted to each project, must be approved by the authorities, which may request adjustments or modifications in the tasks or protocols. This plan must be finished before starting the construction.

Once the plan has been accepted, the construction manager must implement it and ensure its compliance, always under the periodic supervision of the fire & safety manager. In addition to the general regulations, the construction manager will be responsible of informing all workers about the possible peculiarities of the plan.

The main tasks done are the following:

1. Create, implement, and update a fire protection plan adapted to the specific project.
2. Control of evacuation and access points, ensuring that they are always ready and usable. Not even a temporary block is allowed
3. Ensure that combustible waste is professionally removed at least once a day. The temporary storage point will be marked on the site plan.
4. Ensure that hazardous substances within the work are limited to the necessary amount of daily use. The rest must be stored outside the construction site, marking on the site plan the position.
5. Allows and supervises potentially dangerous tasks like, for example, welding, cutting, grinding or sagging. After the completion of the tasks, the expert will be notified and will proceed to carry out a control of the final status.
6. Provides information on the smoking ban and enforces it.
7. Is responsible for the maintenance of fire protection equipment on the site. Ensures that the fire extinguishing equipment present on the site is regularly checked and maintained in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions.

8. Inspect site regularly, documenting all incidents and possible negligence. At least once a week a thorough inspection according to a verification list of the entire construction site should be carried out
9. Communicates and collaborates with local authorities.
10. If a risky situation arises, must initiate the evacuation of the construction site.

The creation of the prevention plan is done using a text processing software and can be communicated via email.

Currently, at HRS, none of the control tasks have been digitized or automated. Requiring the daily presence of a person in charge to control each one of them. On the other hand, the communication processes in case of emergency are not automated either.

Possible incidents are reported immediately and are reflected in daily reports that are stored as records. These reports are created manually using text processing software, supported by photographs if necessary. Daily follow-ups of previous reports are carried out to ensure that the necessary changes have been made.

2.2. Pilot Use Case Safety

The objective will be to comply with the Risk Prevention Law, leaving properly documented all those actions decided to achieve a safe workplace for everyone.

How the preventive action is carried out nowadays by VIAS in the different stages of a project.

- First, before any construction project starts, the Work site Health and Safety Plan must be prepared and approved.
 1. Made by the H&S Manager
 2. Checked by the Site project manager
 3. Approved or not by the H&S coordinator (named by the client)
- Once the H&S plan is approved, we can open the work center and the subcontracting book.
- After that some designations will be done related with preventive action.
 1. H&S site manager
 2. Preventive resources for the site tasks.
 3. Named a person of each subcontractor in charge of safety

The H&S Management on site is made through the participation of different actors with different responsibilities.

1. H&S site manager:
 - a) Check the subcontracts and VIAS documentations
 - b) Continues review of the Health and safety plan, doing whatever needed annexes

- c) Continues inspections visits to site.
 - i. H&S Inspections (recording on paper)
 - 1. No conformity openings
 - 2. Monitoring
 - 3. Improving actions
 - ii. H&S minutes (informative talks)
 - d) Monthly H&S Commission (meeting with subcontractors and coordinator)
 - e) Accidents and incidents reports
 - f) Monthly accident rate report.
2. Preventive resource:
- a) Monitoring of certain assigned task to comply with preventive measures.
3. H&S manager:
- a) Made the H&S plan
 - b) Support to H&S Site managers.
 - c) Periodic visits to site
4. H&S department
- a) Support to H&S manager
 - b) Audits.
5. Foreman
- a) Initial talks about safety before start a task (recording on paper)
6. Site Project Manager
- a) Check and approve any actions related to H&S on site.

VIAS has a computer application for Document and Process Management called “Incaweb” where all the preventive actions are registered.

- 1. ACSS (H&S commission minutes)
 - a) Opening – H&S site manager
 - b) Acceptation - H&S manager
 - c) Approval – Site project manager
- 2. IDI (accident investigation report)
 - a) Opening – H&S site manager
 - b) Review - H&S manager
 - c) Acceptation – Site project manager
 - d) Follow up and closing- H&S site manager
- 3. IMS (Monthly accident rate report)
 - a. Opening – H&S site manager

- b. Follow up and closing- H&S manager
4. INC (no conformity report)
 - a) Opening – H&S site manager
 - b) Review - H&S manager
 - c) Approval – Site project manager
 - d) Follow up –H&S site manager
 - e) closing- project site manager
5. ICTO (Site working conditions in site report)
 - a) Opening – H&S manager
 - b) Review – Site project manager
 - c) Approval and Corrective action plan – Site project manager
 - d) Follow up and closing- H&S manager

The main daily tasks done in site related with fall risk are:

- Supervise task, in order to know/plan which task are going to need new safety resources
- Set new protective equipment, related to the progress of the works
- Supervise safety elements currently set, if they are in place and well set
- Supervise situations that potentially can merge into a fall as could be lack of order and cleanliness
- Safety evaluation
- Reporting of the result of the evaluation
- Informs workers if there are places with a potentially risk of fall.

2.3. Pilot Use Case Scheduling

BIMprove has a layer service (carried out in the planning layer) which, based on the current building situation, reschedules human and material resources. Using the notification and visualization processes BIM@Emergency, BIM@Vehicle, BIM@Anywhere etc., all parties involved in the construction process can be informed about changes in the plan. This will largely prevent over- or under-allocation and conditions that further delay construction work. Furthermore, adaptive planning of the further construction is possible, based on the current situation and a “what if” analysis can be done to support scheduling options. As rescheduling has direct influence on cost of the building process the outputs of the rescheduling will be used in the cost layer to recalculate resulting cost.

The main tasks related to Scheduling are:

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1. Master Schedule with milestones developed and agreed with Client (Project manager + Planner)
2. Contracting of subcontractors and suppliers (Project manager)
3. Detailing of Master Schedule and Phase Scheduling (In collaboration with all involved parties)
4. Look-Ahead planning 4 - 8 weeks (with all involved parties)
5. Weekly work planning and updating of the Phase Plan (with all involved parties)
6. Checklist (app-based) - monitoring progress and status (Foremen/team leader)
7. Daily stand up meetings - Status and today's tasks (with all involved parties)
8. Production-work / installation (workers)
9. On-site verification of built elements and quality checks and documentation (QA Officer)
10. Analysis of the following tasks based on possible deviations (all involved parties)
11. As-built verification and documentation (Surveyor)

The tasks related to Scheduling are based on the process and feedback loop in Last Planner System (as shown in the following figure).

Figure 1 Last Planner System

3. Desired state

Based on the opinion of the experts, it is necessary to establish a clear objective that defines the direction in which to continue developing the use cases, although this objective is outside the scope of this project.

What would be the ideal results? and what about the processes and/or tools?

3.1. Pilot Use Case Fire

The ideal state is obviously one in which there are no personal or material damages while ensuring compliance with regulations. For this, digitization and automation play a transversal role, facilitating on the one hand the access and analysis of information to managers, and on the other, relevant information and warnings of hazard situations to workers. Digitization will allow construction members access to important information as well as relevant warning / notices in order to reduce dangerous situations as much as possible.

Summarizing, all the information that can be centralized, documented and linked to the digital twin / platform, will expand the capabilities of the system, increasing the chances of success in prevention tasks.

After interviewing the experts who carry out their day-to-day activities in this area, we can mention a list of improvements that could be implemented and digitized, having a very positive impact on the execution of their tasks and, therefore, on the control of risk situations.

- Automated emergency ways control system: Through a warning notification system to construction manager, as well as to the person in charge of safety and fire prevention, this system should be able to differentiate between elements in transit and static elements (configurable time) to avoid false alarms.
- Digitized control and communication system for deposits of flammable / dangerous substances: The system should be capable of locating in the digital twin the position and status of the deposits of combustible materials. Specifically, should be able to:
 - Daily communication to workers the position of hazardous materials warehouses, as well as flammable waste deposits. reminding them of the local regulations for the use and cleaning of this type of substance.
 - Allow to monitor the status or level of warehouses / deposits, as well as send alerts to those responsible in case of exceeding previously established levels.
 - Notify the authorities of its position, content and level in case of emergency.

- Dangerous tasks control system: List and send to those responsible all the dangerous tasks that may be foreseen within a period of X days (configurable) and compare them with possible incompatibilities.
 - Receive alert in case of displacement of planned tasks to another moment in which an incompatibility occurs.
 - The system should allow subcontractors to request permission to perform dangerous tasks. This same system should allow the manager to evaluate the situation and approve, delay or cancel the request. Documenting the entire process and those involved.
- Location (in digital twin) and status monitoring of fire extinguishing equipment
- Linking inspection tasks, control and communication of incidents to the digital twin: Being able to link the result of the weekly / daily inspection tasks to elements of the digital twin (BCF format style), maintaining a history of evolution, changes and people / companies involved.
- Fire planning tool based on different construction phases, having the ability to draw or introduce elements depending on the construction phase in order to evaluate different possibilities. Use as control panel, linked with Digital Twin, all information layers and even sensors in construction site (Sensors of deposits, fire extinguisher equipment, entry exits, container electricity, dangerous tasks...)

3.2. Pilot Use Case Safety

Thanks to the Risk Assessment Plan developed in the pilot use case, a BIM safety model will be build, it will be our starting point, our “**to be**”.

Then a Safety Digital Twin will be done thanks to the inspections done by the different sensors, that will be used in the project, with the objective of detecting what is the real situation of the site, while it’s go ahead, it is our “**really be**”.

It good to clarify that in safety a collective protection equipment is understood as a set of elements, for example a safety barrier is conform by two posts, a top and mid rail and a Toe board, if one of these elements is missing, is bad set, or has been modified, it is not going to work properly, so it will be consider as a “**no protection element**”.

Figure 2 Safety element

Once the inspection has been done the Safety Digital Twin will fight against the BIM safety model in order to detect inconsistencies in the safety elements defined in the model, that will help experts to take the decisions that will contribute to reduce or eliminate the unsafe situation associated.

If any inconsistency is detected an alarm will appear, related with the evaluation done regarding the impact of the situation.

Figure 3 Comparison of safety elements

3.3. Pilot Use Case Scheduling

The desired ideal result would be a state where the BIMprove system and the joint project organization, based on the current building situation, reschedules human and material resources. Using the notification and visualization of the processes to all parties involved in the construction process, changes in the plan are distributed. The goal is to prevent over-or under-allocation and conditions that further delay construction work. Furthermore, adaptive planning of further construction is possible, based on the current situation, and a “what if” analysis can be done to

support scheduling options. As rescheduling has a direct influence on the cost of the building process, the outputs of the rescheduling will be used in the cost layer to recalculate the cost.

The **desired state would require processes** and tools which are fully integrated in an ecosystem. Furthermore, it is desired that this ecosystem runs as an autonomous process, based on both physical and process robots, and integrations directly between the solutions in the ecosystem.

4. BIMprove list of functionalities

The following list shows all those new or improved tasks by implementing BIMprove, compared to a build based solely on BIM, and how are these can be related to the PUC's daily work.

Table 1 BIMprove list of functionalities

ID	Functionality name	Functionality description	Input	Output	Task(s) related	PUC related
1	BIM2Path	Creating feasible paths based on the user-input. Waypoints in the correct coordinate frame, also flight velocities, UAV-orientation, camera triggers and camera angles are calculated	Flight with some interaction with an operator (e.g. a start permission)	Waypoint structure (file or data struct)	Fire: Task 2, 3, 4, 5, 7 Safety : Task 1,3, 4 Scheduling: 6, 7, 9, 10, 11	Fire, safety & Scheduling
2	Path2Flight2Images	Flight with some interaction with an operator	a list of points (coordinates) from	Photos stored on on-board SD-card-	Fire: Task 2, 3, 5, 7	Fire, safety & Scheduling

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ID	Functionality name	Functionality description	Input	Output	Task(s) related	PUC related
		(e.g. a start permission)	BIM2Path Functionality		Safety : Task 1,3, 4 Schedul ing: 6, 7, 9, 10, 11	
3	Images2Pointclouds	Obtaining point-cloud based on photogrammetry processes	Photos stored on on-board SD-card obtained with Path2Flight2Images functionality	Point-clouds on PC	Fire: Task 2, 7 Safety : Task 3,4,5 Schedul ing: 6, 7, 9, 10, 11	Fire, Safety & Scheduling
4	Capture Thermal Images	Thermal images are captured manually or by drone	Request for thermal data on specific spot	Thermal images of specific location	Fire: Task 3, 4, 5 Safety : Task 7 Schedul ing: 9, 10, 11	Fire, Safety & Scheduling
5	Use of Tags/Markers	Increase of accuracy on Image2Pointcl	Markers / tags	Additional informati	Fire: Task 7	Fire, Safety & Scheduling

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ID	Functionality name	Functionality description	Input	Output	Task(s) related	PUC related
		oud functionality as well as adding global coordinates (or specific/local coordinate system) to the captured data		on concerning global/specific position. Additional accuracy	Safety : Task 1,3,4 Scheduling: 6, 9	
6	Detection of safety structures	Detect safety structures and untidy places in images	Images of construction site stored in server	Safety barriers, safety nets and untidy places annotated in the images. Results of the detection service stored in the database that can be queried through a specific API develop	Fire: Task 2, 5, 6, 8 Safety : Task 1,2,3,4, 5,6,7	Fire & Safety

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ID	Functionality name	Functionality description	Input	Output	Task(s) related	PUC related
				d for risk data retrieval.		
7	BIM2XR	<p>VR: Import BIM into VR environment. Allows to show/hide models, view parameters, manage BCF reports, time sliding for 4D and multiuser</p> <p>MR and tablets: Show model on 3rd person, allowing rotate, scale, hide/show layers and interacting with floor plan. Also showing digital twin on first person. (adding marking tools, notes or measure distances only</p>	<p>BIM model + BIMprove data generated.</p> <p>Markers are needed for MR and tablets</p>	<p>VR Multiuser environment (MR) Hololens user experience</p> <p>Android tablet experience</p>	<p>Fire: Task 1</p> <p>Safety : Task 1</p> <p>Scheduling: 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11</p>	Fire, Safety & Scheduling

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ID	Functionality name	Functionality description	Input	Output	Task(s) related	PUC related
		available on MR devices).				
8	Schedule import/export	Read Microsoft Project file. Add new tasks and milestones to an existing project. Includes a database Read/Write functionality.	Current task list (gantt) + BIMprove generated data	modified planification on task list (gantt)	Fire: Task 5, 8 Safety : Task 1,2 Scheduling: 1, 3	Fire, Safety & Scheduling
9	Model version control	Allows to detect changes between IFC file revisions	Revision of IFC-file	Colored IFC-file based on changes	Scheduling: 3, 4, 5	Scheduling
10	Identify geometry	Check building progress by identifying geometry (from image2pointcloud & laser scan output) expected according to IFC reference model	Point cloud of building IFC-file of building Gantt data (task list)	BCF – summary of deviations	Fire: Task 7 Safety : Task 1,2 Scheduling: 6, 7, 9, 10, 11	Fire, Safety & Scheduling

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ID	Functionality name	Functionality description	Input	Output	Task(s) related	PUC related
11	Detection of miscellaneous elements in point clouds	Filter point cloud based on found IFC-elements (point-cloud segmentation functionality output), check if large objects still exist in point cloud	Point cloud of building	BCF – summary of material	Fire: Task 2, 3, 8 Safety : Task 2 Scheduling: 6, 7 9, 10, 11	Fire, Safety, Scheduling
12	Point-cloud segmentation	sampled point cloud for visualization, filtering point, allowing a way to the user to identify different geometries/objects	Point cloud of building	Down sampled point cloud	Scheduling: 6, 7 9, 10, 11	Scheduling
13	Bluetooth Low Energy localization	Allows to know if any person is inside any of the located areas. Also allows to know how many persons are located inside each located area	BLE tag ID, RSSI	Push to Database	Fire: Task 9 & 10 Safety : Task 6,7 Scheduling: 4, 5, 7	Fire, Safety & Scheduling

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ID	Functionality name	Functionality description	Input	Output	Task(s) related	PUC related
14	Daily Decision	list of issues (BCF), allowing to accept, reject or request more information (i.e., scans, images...)	BCF list	updated BCF list	Fire: Task 6, 8 Safety : Task 1,2,3,4, 5,6,7 Scheduling: 5, 7	Fire, Safety & Scheduling
15	Heat Map of Worker Position	Show worker/vehicle position in 2D map in real-time (also given interval, day, week, month)	Thermal images	Thermal map	Fire: Task 2 Safety : Task 7 Scheduling: 4, 5, 7	Fire, Safety & Scheduling
16	Schedule Inspection	shows the GANTT chart for the projects, helping to visualize expected Vs executed.	Gantt diagram + BIMprove data	Graphics and list of tasks (expected, delayed, executed ...)	Fire: Task 5, 8 Safety : Task 1 Scheduling: 5, 7	Fire, Safety & Scheduling
17	Schedule and BIM links	Shows task and 3D model on the same split screen,	Gantt + 3D model (IFC)	4D Simulations	Fire: Task 5, 8	Fire,

ID	Functionality name	Functionality description	Input	Output	Task(s) related	PUC related
		allowing to link a task with a 3D geometry (IFC).			Safety : Task 1,2 Scheduling: 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 10	

5. Achievable state

The achievable state defines exactly how the use case will be implemented in the pilot project, emphasizing into existing improved tasks and the new ones (see Table 1).

Due to the research nature of the project and the limitation of time, the area of action has to be delimited to be able to focus the effort, however, the tasks or functionalities that may emerge from this research won't be limited, leaving the possibility of adding more tasks or improvements even during the execution of the pilot projects. To carry out the evaluation of the requirements of these potential new tasks, the consortium will use the sprint system agreed during the planning phase.

5.1. Pilot Use Case Fire

The following table shows the BIMprove functionalities that will be used in the daily development of the pilot use case.

Table 2 Pilot Use Case Fire functionalities

	Daily Tasks										
	Implement Strategy	Evacuation & access points	Storage point	Clean site.	minimize substances on	Supervise tasks	Inform Workers	Fire equipment. Maintains	Reporting (BCF)	Local authorities	Evacuate
BIM2Path		X	X			X		X			
Path2Flight2Images		X	X			X		X			
Images2Pointclouds		X						X			
Capture Thermal Images			X			X					
Use of Tags/Markers											
Detection of safety structures		X				X	X		X		
BIM2XR	X										

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BIMprove Functionalities	Schedule import/export					x					
	Model version control										
	Identify geometry							x			
	Detection of misc-elements in point clouds		x	x					x		
	Point-cloud segmentation										
	Bluetooth Low Energy localization									x	x
	Daily Decision						x		x		
	Heat Map of Worker Position		x								
	Schedule Inspection					x					
	Schedule and BIM links					x					
	<i>Total</i>	1	6	4	0	7	2	4	3	1	1

Figure 4 HRS Daily tasks overview

Comments

The flights with thermal cameras a few minutes before the daily closing, will allow detecting those potentially dangerous hot areas for the work that have gone unnoticed. In this way, it will be possible to avoid the appearance of fires during work closing hours that have been caused by previous work with heat. It should be remembered that these types of situations are, together with uncontrolled electrical devices, those that cause the greatest risk situations.

5.2. Pilot Use Case Safety

The following table shows the BIMprove functionalities that will be used in the daily development of the pilot use case:

Table 3 Pilot Use Case Safety functionalities

BIMprove Functionalities	Daily Tasks							
	Supervise task	Set new protective equipment	Supervise safety elements currently	Supervise potentially situations that can	Safety evaluation	Reporting	Inform workers	
BIM2Path	x		x	x				
Path2Flight2Images	x		x	x				
Images2Pointclouds			x	x	x			
Capture Thermal Images							x	
Use of Tags/Markers	x		x	x				
Detection of safety structures	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	

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	BIM2XR	x						
	Schedule import/export	x	x					
	Model version control							
	Identify geometry	x	x					
	Detection of misc-elements in point clouds		x					
	Point-cloud segmentation							
	Bluetooth Low Energy localization						x	x
	Daily Decision	x	x	x	x	x	x	
	Heat Map of Worker Position							x
	Schedule Inspection	x						
	Schedule and BIM links	x	x					
	<i>Total</i>	10	6	6	6	3	3	4

Figure 5 VIAS Daily tasks overview

Comments

As a starting point we are going to have a BIM safety model based on the Risk Assessment Plan.

The digital twin will be build based on the inspection done by the ground robot, the drones and mainly by the humans.

As the sensors set on the robots are not able to detect the collective protective equipment's as a set of elements it will only help experts to know if the element is in place or not and them the human will evaluate if it is well mounted or if any part is missing, it means that the human will be the one that will do the inspection in depth, evaluating if the scenario is safe or not, according to the methodology defined in the Deliverable 1.8.

The person in charge of doing the safety inspection, will evaluate the situation in a "device", thanks to a table that sum up all the possible situation that can merge into a fall risk, in order to obtain the impact of the risk detected, defining what is observed and locate it in a 3d model.

Related with this result BIMprove will send an alert to all affected personal showing the impact of certain risk associated to an area.

5.3. Pilot Use Case Scheduling

The following table shows the BIMprove functionalities that will be used in the daily development of the pilot use case:

Table 4 Pilot Use Case Scheduling functionalities

BIMprove Functionalities	Daily Tasks																
	As-built verification	Analysis of the	On-site verification	Production on-work	Status and monitoring	Weekly work	Look-Ahead	Detailing of Master Contracting	Master Schedule								
BIM2Path												X	X		X	X	X
Path2Flight2Images												X	X		X	X	X
Images2Pointclouds												X	X		X	X	X
Capture Thermal Images															X	X	X
Use of Tags/Markers												X			X		
Detection of safety structures																	
BIM2XR	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Schedule import/export	X			X													

D1.7 Use-Case requirements

Model version control			x	x	x						
Identify geometry						x	x		x	x	x
Detection of misc-elements in point clouds						x	x		x	x	x
Point-cloud segmentation						x	x		x	x	x
Bluetooth Low Energy localization				x	x		x				
Daily Decision					x		x				
Heat Map of Worker Position				x	x		x				
Schedule Inspection					x		x				
Schedule and BIM links	x	x	x	x	x		x				
<i>Total</i>	3	1	4	5	7	8	12	1	9	8	8

Figure 6 AFG Daily tasks overview

Comments

As in Chapter 3 Desired State, it is desired that all processes are automated and autonomously run, although this probably won't be achievable in the Pilot Use Case. Therefore, a semiautomatic ecosystem supported with some human involvement is considered feasible.

6. BIMprove requirements

After knowing what functionalities will be implemented by each industrial partner and for what, it is necessary to carry out an analysis to determine the possible requirements that the construction site, the hardware and the users may have. The focus will be in both BIM and non BIM related needs.

Table 5 BIMprove requirements (part 1)

ID	Functionality name	PUC Related	PUC	BIM related	Other Requisties (No BIM related)	Level of Geometry (LoG)				
						Link with geometry?	Require specific 3D Model?	3D related?	Element	Specific requirements?
1	BIM2Path	yes	Fire, safety & Scheduling	yes	<p>In a possible way, previously ensure a clean way (no obstacle), focusing attention on movable tools/elements, like, for example, ladders, doors...</p> <p>Referenced to BIM geometry but based on current status of real geometry. Requires an accurate status of all possible collisions on the path, also on Z axis.</p> <p>Requires a way of positioning the drones. Including a tag/marker model or positioning the drone station into the coordinate model.</p>	yes	no, but may require work site model (including scaffolding, cranes, containers, barrier...)	Entire model Spaces	coordinate	<p>correct dimension and position of elements (LoD 200)</p> <p>Information about coordinates of the point 0,0,0 (IfcSite)</p> <p>Modelled interior and exterior IfcSpaces</p> <p>Information about different possible buildings (IfcBuilding), levels (IfcBuildingStorey) and spaces (IfcSpaces)</p>

D1.7 Use-Case requirements

2	Path2Flight2Images	yes	Fire, safety & Scheduling	yes	Good light conditions flight authorisation weather conditions starting/ending time Scheduling (expected geometry on that date)	yes	no, but may require work site model (including scaffolding, cranes, containers, barrier...)	Entire coordinate model Spaces	correct dimension and position of elements (LoD 100-200)
3	Images2Pointclouds	yes	Fire, safety & Scheduling	yes	Resulting cloud must have the same coordinate georeferenced point (x,y,z) as BIM model in order to be able to overlap results into BIMprove	yes	no	reference point	no
4	Capture Thermal Images	yes	Fire, Safety	no	execute at the end of the working hours.	yes	require work site model (including waste areas, storage areas...)	all objects including combustible materials. Dangerous areas because potential fire hazards due to combustible material storage or machinery	correct dimension and position of elements (LoD 200) spaces modelled
5	Use of Tags/Markers	yes	Fire, Safety & Scheduling	yes	Placing markers on reality according to position on digital model and ensure its visibility.	yes	Yes/no	host/guest entity system?	correct dimension and position of elements (LoD 200) no
6	Detection of safety structures	yes	Fire, Safety	yes	-	yes	yes. Safety model or 2D equivalent. maybe as improvement of the site model.	barriers, nets, covers...	Approximate dimension and position of elements (LoD 100)

D1.7 Use-Case requirements

7	BIM2XR	yes	Fire, Safety & Scheduling	yes	For VR: Specific container with enough space and specific hardware. For AR: Good light conditions (underground areas). Internet on the entire construction area if the app is not able to execute on offline modus. Clean visibility of the surrounded markers.	Yes	For AR Marker model is required	Entire coordinate model	For VR: no For AR: correct dimension and position of elements (LoD 200)
8	Schedule import/export	yes	Fire, Safety & Scheduling	yes	-	yes	no	Entire coordinate model	correct dimension and position of elements (LoD 200) 3D elements segmented accordingly to planning
9	Model version control	yes	Scheduling	yes	-	yes	no	Entire coordinate model	-
10	Identify geometry	yes	Fire, Safety & Scheduling	yes	input deviation tolerance according to national laws (can vary depending on the country)	yes	point-cloud	Entire coordinate model + site model	precision on point-cloud (use of markers functionality) IFC LoD 300+
11	Detection of misc-elements in point clouds	yes	Fire, Safety & Scheduling	no	-	-	-	-	-
12	Point-cloud segmentation	yes	Scheduling	no	-	-	-	-	-
13	Bluetooth Low Energy localization	yes	Fire, Safety & Scheduling	yes	receptor must work using battery. (There is no possibility to use cable)	yes (spaces)	no	spaces (interior and exterior)	Approximate dimension and position of elements (LoD 100)

D1.7 Use-Case requirements

14	Daily Decision	yes	Fire, Safety & Scheduling	yes	-	-	-	Entire coordinate model + site model	-
15	Heat Map of Worker Position	yes	Fire, Safety & Scheduling	yes	if its going to be done by thermal camaras the monitoring should be continuous	yes (spaces)	no	-	-
16	Schedule Inspection	yes	Fire, Safety & Scheduling	no	-	-	-	-	-
17	Schedule and BIM links	yes	Fire, Safety & Scheduling	yes		yes	no	Entire coordinate model + site model	3D elements segmented accordingly to planning

Table 6 BIMprove requirements (part 2)

ID	Functionality name	Level of Information (LoI)				
		ifcEntity	Attribute	Property	Existing parameter?	Format type
1	BIM2Path	IfcCoordinateReferenceSystem*	Name	-	yes	-
		IfcSite	SiteAddress, RefLatitude, RefLongitude, RefElevation	-	yes	-
		IfcBuilding	ElevationOfRefHeight	-	yes	-
		IfcBuildingStorey	Elevation	-	yes	-
		IfcSpace	Name	IsExternal	yes	-
2	Path2Flight2Images	IfcCoordinateReferenceSystem*	Name	-	yes	-
		IfcSite	SiteAddress, RefLatitude, RefLongitude, RefElevation	-	yes	-
		IfcBuilding	ElevationOfRefHeight	-	yes	-
		IfcBuildingStorey	Elevation	-	yes	-
		IfcSpace	Name	IsExternal	yes	-
3	Images2Pointclouds	IfcSite	RefLatitude, RefLongitude, RefElevation	-	yes	-
		IfcCoordinateReferenceSystem				

D1.7 Use-Case requirements

4	Capture Thermal Images	any ifcEntity	combustible	-	yes	-
5	Use of Tags/Markers	IfcProxyElementBuilding	Type = QR for Drone Name = ID	-	yes yes	- -
6	Detection of safety structures	ifcRailing, ifcCovering ifcTaskTime with its subtypes	-	-	yes	-
7	BIM2XR	any ifcEntity	-	-	-	-
8	Schedule import/export	ifcTaskTime with its subtypes	-	-	yes	-
9	Model version control	any ifcEntity	-	Keep same GUID for each element. ifcTimeStamp for version control	yes	-
10	Identify geometry	any ifcEntity ifcTaskTime with its subtypes	-	GUID	yes	-
11	Detection of misc-elements in point clouds	-	-	-	-	-
12	Point-cloud segmentation	-	-	-	-	-

D1.7 Use-Case requirements

13	Bluetooth Low Energy localization	ifcSpace	-	IsExternal type name	yes	-
14	Daily Decision	-	-	-	-	-
15	Heat Map of Worker Position	-	-	-	-	-
16	Schedule Inspection	-	-	-	-	-
17	Schedule and BIM links	any ifcEntity	-	-	-	-

